

Place and Displacement: Depiction of Marginality in Temsula Ao's Short Story *Soaba*

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Abstract

In Postcolonial Theory, place is associated with identity and displacement with its loss. This paper looks at the depiction of effects of displacement on Adivasi communities in literature. The theoretical basis is derived mainly from the relevant ideas discussed in The Empire Writes Back. Both material and cultural effects of displacement are theorised, along with their intersection with appropriation into an alien economic system. This concept is studied in the short story Soaba by Temsula Ao from Nagaland.

Keywords: Adivasi Literature, Postcolonial Theory, Marginalisation, Place and Displacement

Introduction

Place and displacement is identified as a “major feature of post-colonial literatures” (Ashcroft et al. 8), the feature being an “identifying relationship between self and place” (8) brought into crisis by the displacement of the colonised. D.E.S. Maxwell has theorised this in terms of the “disjunction between place and language” and questioned the “‘appropriateness’ of an imported language to describe the experience of a place in post-colonial societies”(qtd. in Ashcroft et al. 23). The writers of *The Empire Writes Back* have, however, broadened this idea, stating:

“A valid sense of self may have been eroded by *dislocation*, resulting from migration, the experience of enslavement, transportation, or ‘voluntary’ removal for indentured labour. Or it may have been destroyed by *cultural denigration*, the conscious and unconscious oppression of indigenous personality and culture by a supposedly superior racial or cultural model.” (9; original italics).

Maxwell has applied his theory to mainly two groups. The first is the settler colonies like “the United States, New Zealand and Australia” and the second, the invaded ones like “India and Nigeria”(qtd. in Ashcroft et al. 24).According to Maxwell, in both the cases, there was a “disjuncture” between the place and the language. *The Empire Writes Back*, while exposing the shortcomings of Maxwell’s model, adds the important third example of the Caribbean, where people from “Africa, India, China, the ‘Middle East’ and Europe”(24) were uprooted and transplanted into a different region. The quotation above, about the valid sense of self, is applied mainly to this third group. The paper is mainly based on this particular proposition, of loss of (cultural) identity of a marginalised group due to displacement from their place.

In the context of the Adivasis, this idea needs to be given some historical perspective, before moving to its depiction in literature. The East India Company established the Zamindari, the Ryotwari and the Mahalwari systems in various parts of India in the first quarter of the 19th century. Moyukh Mahtab traces the migration of Santhals after this. The Company “demarcated the Damin I Koh region in present day Jharkhand” in 1832. The Company then invited the Santhals, living then in Bengal and Odisha at that time, to migrate to this region as agricultural labour. The Santhals did this willingly, as they were promised “land and other economic amenities”. However, they were lent money “at exorbitant rates” and “were forced into bonded labour” when they were unable to return it. Similar pattern operated for Kol, Ho and Munda tribes. This is a case of displacement with the promise of “indentured labour”, which on the face of it, is simply economic exploitation. However, this was actually accommodation of these Adivasi tribes into a completely different

economic model, one based on capitalistic hierarchical division of labour, with the Company at the top, the various tax collectors like zamindars in the middle and the Adivasis, as labours, at the bottom. This was a cultural shift, based on displacement, leading to exploitation.

At this point, it must be noted that even after political decolonisation of India, similar methods have been operational. Post-independence, coal mining led to similar exploitation of the Santhals.

While this example presents an intersection of colonial strategies with economic exploitation, another enforcer of displacement have been the armed forces. An example of this is the case of Salwa Judum in Chhattisgarh. The Salwa Judum, which literally translates to “people’s peace movement” (“NDTV”) was a force formed in 2005 by the government. It consisted of Adivasis who were given arms and positions as Special Police Officers to fight against the menace of Naxalism. One of the strategies used by these “officers” was to empty villages “in the name of safety” (ibid) and move them to camps. The camps were “like prisons”; “no one was permitted to go into forests to collect Mahua, Tendu (leaves)...their lands remained untilled for two years”. (ibid). Again, we see displacement leading to an alteration in economic model; in fact, there’s no substitute model here. More importantly, these are cultural ways of subsistence that are affected. A colonial parallel of this post-colonial example is the infamous Reconcentrado Policy employed in 1897 in Cuba by Spanish Governor General Valeriano Weyler.

It should also be noted that most Adivasi tribes believe in animism, that is the existence of spirits in nature. Their lives are then shaped according to this belief system of interacting with these “spirits” and in turn, with nature. Along with the economic factors seen above, displacement also results removal from a cosmological world. Displacement thus, used as a strategy of marginalisation, causes a cultural shift and has existed in both colonial and post-colonial times. It is further complicated due to urbanisation and new systems of governance, as will be seen in the case study.

Case Study

Soaba by Temsula Ao

This short story by Ao is set in the Mokokchung town of Nagaland in the late 1950s, a time when insurgency was at its peak in the state. It tells the story of Soaba, a possibly mentally stunted man, who is caught in the “the whirlwind sweeping through the land and creating havoc in people’s lives”. (Ao 9). This “whirlwind” has been caused by many factors – urbanisation, creation of cosmopolitan societies and most importantly, creation of a force called the Home Guards by the government. The Guards were locals whose job was to guide the armed forces into the terrain and also catch and torture suspected collaborators of the insurgents. The story zooms in on Boss, the leader of one such Guards’ group. It tells how Soaba, mostly a nomad, settles at Boss’ home and eventually gets killed.

The displacement in the story is very subtle. The story does, as a background, tell us how the army used an explicit strategy called ‘grouping’, where entire villages were “dislodged from their ancestral sites”(11), similar to the examples in Chhattisgarh and Cuba seen above. In the case of Mokokchung and similar townships, “people had migrated...as petty clerks in government offices, teachers...traders...” (10). It can be argued that this was a good shift that promoted “development” through upward mobility. However, this is a cultural shift, as people were appropriated into new systems of governance and economy. Contradictory to the objectives of democracy, it did not empower them. Rimi Tadu, says in the context of a similar process in Arunachal Pradesh, “they (who took up government jobs) were merely representatives and mouthpieces of the administrators...”¹² (9). Further, youth began to be alienated from their culture and even mocking it. In the context of Arunachal again, J.L. Dawar observes that the new Christian converts there started “ridiculing the indigenous faith and practices”. (910). Ao lays down a similar observation in

the present text, "...a new environment was emerging and overtaking the old ways, and youngsters growing up in such a place (townships) began to think of themselves as the new generation."¹⁴ (10). In its connection with coloniality, this was a strategy in line with Thomas Macaulay's dictum – creation of a class, tribal in origin, but owing allegiance to the state and not the people. It creates a hierarchy while alienating people from their culture.

The worst manifestation of this strategy was the Home Guards. The story depicts minute changes taking place in the Boss' lifestyle – "he started wearing new and fashionable clothes and flashy rings on his fingers" (Ao 13). At the loud parties at his house, *Hindi* songs would play (18), signaling the penetration of another (dominant) culture. The greatest problem was, however, the creation of "a new hierarchy" (13) and the Boss' ambiguous, powerless position in it. The Guards were clearly "beyond the law and civil rights" (12) and means to perpetuate "sinister abuses" (18) on people. This is unlike the government jobs which are at least within the law. Further, in spite of the power he wielded, he was always under the "leash" (17) of his handlers, the government. The "leash" in the case of government employees was economic and bureaucratic; for the Boss, it is directly in the form of muscle power.

All this results in a larger cultural change, which is actually the central theme of the story – "the conflict of interests...eating into the moral fabric of the society where friendship and loyalty were the casualties." (12). Adivasi communities have been traditionally close-knit and communal in their existence. Ruby Hembrom, in the context of the Santhals' oral tradition, says that experience (of life) is of a "shared community" and "corporal". This is reflected even in art. K Ayyappa Paniker says that the stories of Adivasis are "not the experience of any particular individual member" (122), but of the community. This social structure is ruptured due to the "new hierarchy". A subtle example of this in the present text is that due to the Boss' position and threats he possessed for himself, the "sedate and domesticated lifestyle" of his wife also changed: "she could not go anywhere without a bodyguard and her friends and relatives could not come to the house freely..."²⁴ (Ao 14-5). On a larger level, the Guards started suspecting and torturing their own people.

It is extremely important to note that the insurgents were doing the same thing; Ao notes, "Through a method not dissimilar to 'conscriptio'...many rural adults had to abandon family and fieldwork and were inducted in the 'underground' army of freedom fighters."²⁵ (10). This was also displacement resulting in alteration of cultural values. The lives of ordinary people were caught in the cross fire between the state's armed forces and the insurgents.

Conclusions

Displacement, thus, is seen in two ways in the short story – on the physical level of 'grouping' and migration and the metaphorical level of cultural shifts. These are indeed colonial methods in which both land and culture are appropriated. Further, the coloniality intertwined with economic exploitation. Stories like *Soaba* highlight this marginalisation and indicate that for sustainable development, it is essential that the locals be empowered and their cultures be respected.

References

1. Ao, Temsula. *These Hills Called Home: Stories from a War Zone*. India: Penguin Random House; Zubaan, 2006.
2. Ashcroft, Bill, et al. *The Empire Writes Back*. Taylor & Francis e-Library, 2004.
3. Dawar, Jagdish Lal. "CONTENDING HEGEMONIES IN THE NORTH-EAST INDIA: RESPONSES TO RELIGIOUS CONVERSION AMONG THE ADI TRIBES OF ARUNACHAL PRADESH SINCE

- 1950'S." *Proceedings of the Indian History Congress*, vol. 60, 1999, pp. 908–917. *JSTOR*, www.jstor.org/stable/44144162. Accessed 25 May 2021
4. Hebrom, Ruby. "The Life and After-Life of Orality: Karam Binti and the Santal Identity." University of Zurich, Zurich. 13 Sept. 2018. Lecture. www.musethno.uzh.ch/dam/jcr:285c8a14-6668-4cde-990f-2dfca3bdfa19/rh_lecture.pdf
 5. Moyukh, Mahtab. "When the Santhals Rebelled". *The Daily Star*, 25 June 2016, <https://www.thedailystar.net/in-focus/when-the-santhals-rebelled-1245196>
 6. Paniker, K. Ayyappa. *Indian Narratology*. New Delhi: Indira Gandhi National Centre for the Arts; New Delhi: Sterling Publishers, 2003.
 7. "Special Report: The weapons of peace (Aired: February 2008)." *YouTube*, uploaded by NDTV, 6 September, 2013, www.youtube.com/watch?v=V0hFGFDJRT0
 8. Tadu, Rimi. "The Philosophers of NEFA." *Journal of Tribal Intellectual Collective India*, Vol 2, Issue 2, No 1, pp. 1-29. www.daltrijournals.org/JTICI/V2I2No1.php

